

Article

Rootstock Effects on Tomato Fruit Composition and Pollinator Preferences in Tomato

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Abstract: Food security is threatened by climate change and associated abiotic stresses that affect the flowering stage and the biochemistry of flowers and fruits. In tomato, managed insect pollination and grafting elite tomato varieties onto robust rootstocks are widely practiced commercially to enhance tomato crop profitability, particularly under suboptimal conditions. However, little is known about rootstock–pollinator interactions and their impact on the chemical composition of fruit. In this study, a commercial tomato F1 hybrid (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) was self-grafted and grafted onto a set of experimental rootstocks and cultivated under optimal and saline (75 mM NaCl) conditions in the presence of managed bumblebee pollinators (*Bombus terrestris*). The number of visits (VN) and total visiting time (TVT) by pollinators to different grafted plants were monitored through an RFID (radio-frequency identification) tracking system, while targeted metabolites (hormones, sugars, and organic and amino acids) and mineral composition were analyzed in the fruit juice by UHPLC-MS and ICP-OES, respectively. Pollinator foraging decisions were influenced by the rootstocks genotype and salinity treatment. Experimental rootstocks predominantly increased pollinator attraction compared to the self-grafted variety. Interestingly, the pollinator parameters were positively associated with the concentration of abscisic acid, salicylic acid, malate and fumarate, and tyrosine in salinized fruits. Moreover, a high accumulation of sodium was detected in the fruits of the plants most visited by pollinators, while rootstock genotype-specific responses were found for nitrogen and potassium concentrations. In addition to the known effect on yield, these findings underscore the synergic interactions between rootstocks, pollinators, and environmental stressors on tomato fruit composition.

Keywords: *Bombus terrestris*; bumblebees; fruit quality; metabolomics; rootstock breeding; salinity; *Solanum* sp.

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1. Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated and consumed crops worldwide, valued for its versatility, nutritional content, antioxidant properties, and many health-promoting bioactive compounds [1,2]. However, abiotic stresses like salinity, exacerbated by climate change and poor irrigation practices, pose significant challenges to tomato cultivation. Salinity is especially prevalent in arid and semi-arid climates [3] and disrupts the water uptake and ion balance within a plant, causing physiological and biochemical alterations [4]. These environmental factors impact the biochemical composition of fruits [5–7], including the levels of sugars, acids, proteins, amino acids (particularly proline), and other secondary metabolites [8–10], which are crucial for the taste, nutritional profile, and shelf-life of fruits.

One effective strategy to mitigate the adverse effects of salinity is the use of salt tolerant rootstocks [11–13]. By grafting commercial varieties onto selected rootstocks, growers can improve plant vigor [14] and enhance nutrient and water uptake efficiencies [15], as well as fruit quality and composition [16,17]. In this regard, numerous studies have investigated the impact of rootstocks on the endogenous production of primary and secondary metabolites, including sugars, acids, flavonoids, vitamins, and volatiles, which are important factors that strongly influence the quality of fruit [18]. Additionally, studies concerning the descriptor qualities and composition of tomato fruit from rootstocks subjected to certain environmental conditions have also been reported, particularly in saline environments [17].

Abiotic stresses can also disrupt the delicate balance of ecosystems, affecting the availability and effectiveness of pollinators, which are crucial for ensuring optimal pollination and fruit development. While the sodium in nectar seems to play an important role in pollinator attraction [19,20], studies on the direct effects of salinity stress on plant–pollinator interactions are lacking. Hence, salinity-induced changes in floral rewards, such as nectar and pollen [21,22], may alter the attractiveness of flowers to pollinators, thereby impacting fruit set and yield. Understanding the interaction between salinity and pollinators is essential for developing sustainable agricultural practices that maintain pollination services and maximize fruit quality in saline environments.

Animal pollination is required by 75% of cultivated crops [23]. However, the global decline in pollinator populations [24] has increased interest in exploring the interdependence between crops and pollinators due to their essential role in food production and stability [25,26]. While tomato flowers are self-fertile, their pollination significantly improves with insect intervention [27,28], and recently its use has been developed and applied commercially worldwide to ensure flower fertilization [29]. On the other hand, even though it is well known that pollination positively affects agronomic characteristics, such as fruit set, size, and yield [27,30–32], there is limited research on its impacts on the nutritional value and flavour of tomatoes [33]. Additionally, the metabolomic composition of flowers in response to the foraging decisions of pollinators has been extensively studied [34], but it still remains unclear whether this correlates with the nutritional value of the fruit, and how it is influenced by the rootstock and the saline stress environment.

Therefore, in this study, we hypothesized that tomato rootstocks and salinity influence the foraging decisions of bumblebee pollinators, which, beyond floral traits, is also reflected in the fruit composition and nutritional value of the grafted variety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Plant Material, Grafting, and Growth Conditions

The commercial cherry tomato variety cv. Unidarkwin F1 (Unigenia Semillas S.L.U.) was grafted onto the following experimental rootstocks, which were previously selected for other purposes (Table 1): two accessions of wild tomato species, *Solanum pennellii* C. (accession, LA0716; Penn) and *Solanum pimpinellifolium* L. (LA1589; Pimpi), and hybrids obtained from crosses between introgression lines derived from *S. lycopersicum* cv. M82 x Penn with either LA1589 (76×Pimpi) or *S. lycopersicum* cv. M82 (77× M82), as well as from a cross between the introgression line derived from *S. lycopersicum* (E6203) × *Solanum habrochaites* K. & S. (LA1777) with LA1589 (K×Pimpi). The self-grafted commercial variety Unidarkwin was used as a control (SG). The sowing of scion and rootstock seeds was synchronized to obtain the appropriate stem diameter to ensure grafting viability and homogenous grafted plants. Grafting was carried out using the splicing method at the 2–3 true leaf stage (3–4 weeks after sowing). One month after grafting, they were transplanted to an experimental greenhouse (located in Santomera, Murcia) and cultivated in sacs of 70 L (three plants per sac), using coconut fiber as a substrate, under a drip irrigation system along three bands. All plants (72) were initially irrigated with Hoagland's solution [35], and after 30 days of acclimation under the control conditions, half of the plants were exposed to 0 mM (control; electrical conductivity: 3 dS m⁻¹) and the other half received a saline treatment by adding 75 mM NaCl (electrical conductivity: 11 dS m⁻¹)

to the nutrient solution for 8 weeks (from 30 April to 29 July). Plants receiving the saline treatment were alternated with control plants in groups of twelve plants.

Table 1. Scion–rootstock combinations used in the experiment. The commercial cherry tomato cv. Unidarkwin F1 (UD) was self-grafted (SG) and grafted onto different rootstocks. Different scion–rootstock combinations are denoted by abbreviations according to the rootstock genotype.

Abbreviation	Scion	Rootstock
SG	UD	cv. Unidarkwin (self-grafted)
Penn	UD	<i>Solanum pennellii</i> acc. LA0716
Pimpi	UD	<i>Solanum pimpinellifolium</i> acc. LA1589
76×Pimpi	UD	Introgressed line LA4076 (derived from <i>S. lycopersicum</i> cv. M82 × <i>S. pennellii</i> acc. LA0716) × <i>S. pimpinellifolium</i> acc. LA1589
77×M82	UD	Introgressed line LA4077 (derived from <i>S. lycopersicum</i> cv. M82 × <i>S. pennellii</i> acc. LA0716) × <i>S. lycopersicum</i> cv. M82
K×Pimpi	UD	Introgressed line K (derived from <i>S. lycopersicum</i> E6203 × <i>S. habrochaites</i> LA1777) × <i>S. pimpinellifolium</i> LA1589

During this period, the average greenhouse temperature was 24.9 °C, with an interval of approximately 13 °C between day and night. The concentration of the macro- and micronutrients in both the control and salinized nutrient solution were 4 mM KNO₃, 2 mM KH₂PO₄, 1 mM NH₄NO₃, 5 mM Ca(NO₃)₂, 2 mM MgSO₄, 100 µM Fe 22.64 µM, 3.14 µM Mn, 2.09 µM Zn; 0.60 µM Cu, and 0.05 µM Mo.

2.2. Insect Geopositioning System for Plant × Pollinator Quantification by RFID Monitoring

A bumblebee (*Bombus terrestris*) hive from Agrobio (Almería, Spain) was placed every three weeks to ensure pollination of the 72 plants in the greenhouse between 21 May and 4 July 2021. The preferences of bumblebees were determined using a radio-frequency identification system (RFID) as described by Pérez-Alfocea et al. [36]. The RFID system used is based on a Biomark Small Scale Monitoring System (Biomark, Inc., Boise, ID, USA) and consists of a datalogger connected to 16 different antennas (30 cm diameter) and tags (8–10 mm long). Plants from four different genotypes under the control and the saline conditions were monitored simultaneously. The antennas were placed on selected plants surrounding the flowering trusses and tags were glued to the bumblebee’s abdomen. All RFID signals generated by antennas upon detecting a tag were collected by a datalogger throughout the experiment. The spatio-temporal analysis was performed using an ad hoc developed software (<https://rfidpollinators.ew.r.appspot.com>, accessed on 30 July 2024) to calculate the visit number (VN) and the total visit time (TVT).

2.3. Metabolomic Analyses

After eight weeks of treatment, six to eight ripe tomato fruits per genotype and treatment were harvested, immediately transported to the laboratory, and stored at −20 °C. Thirty tomato juice metabolites, including sugars (sucrose and hexoses, as the sums of fructose and glucose), amino acids (Arg, His, Leu, Lys, Met, Phe, Thr, Trp, Val, Pro, Tyr, Asp, Asn, Glu, Gln, and His), organic acids (malate, succinate, citrate, and fumarate), and the main phytohormones gibberellins (GA₃ and GA₄), cytokinins *trans*-zeatin (tZ) and zeatin riboside (ZR) abscisic acid (ABA), salicylic acid (SA), and the ethylene precursor 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC), were extracted and analyzed as described previously in Albacete et al. and Martínez-Andújar et al. [37,38]. Briefly, pulp tomato juice was extracted using a HELIX juicer (Joseph Joseph, London, UK). The obtained juice was initially passed through a strainer and subsequently filtered using a 0.45 µm pore size filter. The solids were separated by centrifugation (20,000× *g*, 15 min, 4 °C). A total of 10 µL of filtered extracts was injected into a U-HPLC-MS system comprising a Vanquish U-HPLC coupled to an Exactive mass spectrometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) using a heated electrospray ionization interface (HESI) equipped with a 96-microwell plate autosampler and capillary pump. Mass spectra were obtained in the

negative mode using Xcalibur software version 4.3 (ThermoFisher Scientific). To quantify each hormone, calibration curves were constructed for each analyzed component (1, 10, 50, and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and corrected for 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ deuterated internal standards [2H5]tZ, [2H6]ABA, [2H4]SA, and [2H6]JA (Olchemims.r.o., Olomouc, Czech Republic). Recovery percentages ranged between 92 and 95%. To quantify the rest of the metabolites, calibration curves were constructed for each analyzed component, including amino acids (10, 100, 500, and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), organic acids (50, 100, 200, and 400 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), and sugars (10, 50, 100, and 400 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), using a set of standards from the companies Olchemim and Sigma-Aldrich (Merck Group, Darmstadt, Germany).

2.4. Determination of the Mineral Nutrient Concentrations in Tomato Fruit

To determine the mineral composition of the fruit, tomato juice was previously extracted with a HELIX juicer (Joseph Joseph, London, UK). The concentration of macro- (Na, K, Mg, Ca, and P) and micronutrients (B, Cu, Fe, Mn, and Zn) were analyzed. Firstly, the samples were digested by $\text{HNO}_3:\text{HClO}_4$ (2:1 *v/v*) solution. Then, they were analyzed using inductively coupled plasma spectrometry (ICP-OES, Thermo Scientific ICAP 6000 Series). Total C and N concentrations were determined by the combustion method using a TruSpec Micro elemental analyzer (LECO Corporation, St. Joseph, MI, USA).

2.5. Statistical Analysis

For the data analysis, IBM SPSS Statistics 23 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) software and Rstudio 4.3.2 were used. For pollinator preference bar charts, the visit number (VN) and total visit time (TVT) parameters were first rationalized according to the number of days of the experiment and by the average number of flowers per truss (10–15 under the control and 9–14 under the salt stress conditions). Data normality and variance homogeneity were checked using the Shapiro and Levene tests, respectively. In cases of non-normal distribution, significant differences were tested using the Kruskal–Wallis test; otherwise, one-way ANOVA and post hoc Tukey’s tests were performed. For metabolites and ions bar charts, the data were first normalized according to the fresh weights of the samples. For the heatmap, the mean values of the amino acids, sugars, and organic acids were scaled, centered, and log2 transformed, and the “pheatmap” library was used. Finally, for the PCA plots, the varimax method was used.

3. Results

3.1. Pollinator Foraging Activity

Under the optimal conditions, the number of visits by RFID-tagged bumblebees increased concomitantly with the visit duration for plants grafted onto Pimpi, Penn, and $\text{K}\times\text{Pimpi}$ compared to the SG (Figure 1A,B). After 8 weeks of growth under salinity conditions, the number of visits increased mainly for Pimpi (Figure 1A), while the total visit time increased in both the Pimpi and $77\times\text{M82}$ rootstocks (Figure 1B), compared to the SG plants. Unlike the optimal conditions, plants grafted onto $\text{K}\times\text{Pimpi}$ exhibited fewer visits and shorter visit durations relative to the SG (Figure 1A,B).

Figure 1. Cont.

Figure 1. (A) Number and (B) duration of visits expressed as ratios of heterografted plants (see Table 1) with respect to the self-grafted (SG) plants under the control (green) and salinity (pink) conditions. The SG’s average values (dashed line) for visit number and duration, monitored over 14 days, are indicated in each case. The bars represent mean values for 2 to 5 biological replicates + relative SE.

3.2. Hormonal Profile of Fruits and Correlations with Pollinator Preference

3.2.1. 1-Aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic Acid (ACC)

Under the control conditions, fruits from the less visited 76×Pimpi grafted plants exhibited the lowest ACC concentrations, although significant differences among fruits from the different graft combinations were not observed (Figure 2A). Salinity reduced fruit ACC levels between 20 and 30% for all rootstock genotypes (significant reductions observed only for 77×M82), except 76×Pimpi, in which these concentrations were slightly induced compared to the control conditions (Figure 2A). Under conditions of salinity, despite the absence of significant differences in the ACC levels among the graft combinations, a significant positive correlation was found between ACC concentration in the fruits and visit duration (TVT) ($r = 0.68, p \leq 0.01$) (Table S1).

Figure 2. Hormone concentrations in tomato fruit juice of cv. Unidarkwin self-grafted (SG) and grafted onto different rootstocks (see Table 1) and grown under the control (0 mM NaCl; green) and

saline (75 mM NaCl added to the nutrient solution; pink) conditions. Boxplots represent the means of the absolute values of three replicates. (A) ACC, 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid; (B) ABA, abscisic acid; (C) SA, salicylic acid; (D) tZ, *trans*-zeatin; (E) ZR, zeatin riboside; (F) GA₃, gibberellic acid; (G) GA₄, gibberellin GA₄. Significant differences among rootstock genotypes are indicated by different letters and between treatments within each genotype by asterisks (“*” = $p \leq 0.05$; “**” = $p \leq 0.01$ and “***” = $p \leq 0.001$).

3.2.2. Abscisic Acid (ABA)

The ABA concentrations in the control fruits remained stable across all graft combinations, while in salinized fruits, the highest ABA levels were observed in the two most frequently visited rootstocks, Pimpi and, particularly, 77×M82 (significantly higher than that found in the SG) (Figure 2B). Notably, fruit ABA concentrations increased under salinity relative to the control treatment only in these two graft combinations and to a greater extent in 77×M82 (Figure 2B). The fruits most significantly affected by salt were the less preferred grafts 76×Pimpi and SG. Indeed, fruit ABA concentration was positively correlated with both VN and TVT under the control (VN, $r = 0.45$, $p = 0.16$; TVT, $r = 0.63$, $p \leq 0.05$) and salinity (VN, $r = 0.36$, $p = 0.2$; TVT, $r = 0.28$, $p = 0.34$) conditions (Table S1).

3.2.3. Salicylic Acid (SA)

The SA concentrations of the fruit were 16.6–25.8% higher in nonsalinized plants grafted onto highly preferred Pimpi rootstocks compared to other graft combinations, but the differences were significant only compared to the less-visited 76×Pimpi rootstock (Figure 2C). Salinity induced a significant decrease in fruit SA levels across all graft combinations when compared to optimal conditions. The wild parental rootstocks Penn and Pimpi exhibited the highest fruit SA concentrations under salinity conditions, but the differences were not significant (Figure 2C). A slightly positive correlation was found between fruit SA levels and TVT ($r = 0.17$, $p = 0.56$) in salt-treated plants.

3.2.4. Cytokinins

Zeatin riboside (ZR) was more abundant than the free base *trans*-zeatin (tZ) in the analyzed fruits. Under the optimal conditions, the highest concentrations of tZ and ZR were found in fruit from plants grafted onto the highly preferred K×Pimpi rootstock (significant only with respect to the lowly preferred 76×Pimpi) (Figure 2D,E). Salinity reduced CK levels across all graft combinations, to a greater extent in the less-preferred SG (tZ and ZR) and 76×Pimpi (ZR) rootstocks (Figure 2D,E). A negative correlation was found between fruit tZ and pollinator preference parameters in nonsalinized fruits (VN, $r = -0.19$, $p = 0.57$; TVT, $r = -0.41$, $p = 0.21$), while a positive correlation was found between ZR and the number of visits ($r = 0.25$, $p = 0.42$) and total visit time ($r = 0.30$, $p = 0.32$) in salinized fruits (Table S1).

3.2.5. Gibberellins

The GA₃ was 6.6-fold higher than the GA₄ in fruit juice (Figure 2F,G), and GA₃ levels were 2.7–3.9 times higher in K×Pimpi compared to the SG and the other graft combinations under both control and salt stress conditions (Figure 2G). Salinity increased GA₃ levels only in the fruits of plants grafted onto crosses derived from the wild species of *S. pimpinellifolium* (K×Pimpi and, particularly, 76×Pimpi) (Figure 2G). No significant differences in fruit GA₄ levels were observed between genotypes and treatments (Figure 2F). However, a positive correlation was found between GA₄ and both VN ($r = 0.45$, $p = 0.17$) and TVT ($r = 0.55$, $p = 0.08$) in nonsalinized fruits (Table S1).

Overall, the ethylene precursor ACC as well as ABA in the fruit was positively associated with the duration of visit at flowering under salinity conditions, while under optimal conditions fruits of the grafted plants highly preferred by bumblebees also accumulated more ABA (Pimpi and 77×M82), SA (Pimpi) and CKs (K×Pimpi), compared to the SG and less-preferred grafts.

3.3. Metabolites in Fruits

3.3.1. Sugars

The fruit juice of the plants grafted onto the three rootstocks preferred by bumblebees (Pimpi, Penn, and K×Pimpi) accumulated higher levels of hexoses (fructose + glucose) under the control conditions compared to the other graft combinations (Figure 3A). Indeed, hexose concentrations in nonsalinized fruits were positively correlated with both VN ($r = 0.52$, $p = 0.10$) and TVT ($r = 0.55$, $p = 0.08$) (Table S1). Under salinity, fruits from the Penn grafts kept high levels of sugars, while plants grafted onto the longest visited 77×M82 graft registered the lowest levels of sucrose and hexoses under salt stress (Figure 3A).

Figure 3. (A) Heatmap representing the variations in the log₂ values of the mean concentrations of metabolites in the tomato juice of the cv. Unidarkwin F1 self-grafted (SG) and grafted onto different experimental rootstocks (see Table 1) and grown under the control and salinity (75 mM NaCl) conditions. The heat scale indicates the lowest values in blue and the highest values in orange. (B) Relative changes (% of control conditions) in the different graft combinations (see Table 1). Trp, tryptophan; Phe, phenylalanine; Leu, leucine; Thr, threonine; Tyr, tyrosine; Asn, asparagine; Met, methionine; Val, valine; Pro, proline; Gln, glutamine; His, histidine; Asp, aspartate; Arg, arginine; Lys, lysine.

3.3.2. Organic Acids

Under the control conditions, the highest malate, citrate, and fumarate concentrations were registered in the fruits of the highly preferred Penn grafts, while the largest succinate concentration was found in fruits from plants grafted onto 77×M82 (Figure 3A). A significant negative correlation was found between the total concentration of organic acids and VN ($r = -0.71, p \leq 0.05$), TVT ($r = -0.81, p \leq 0.01$), and, particularly, citrate (VN, $r = -0.72, p \leq 0.05$; TVT, $r = -0.813, p \leq 0.01$) in nonsalinized fruits (Table S1). Malate and fumarate concentrations in salinized fruits decreased by 30.7–38.4% compared to the control conditions (Figure 3B), but the highest concentrations were found in the longest-visited grafts 77×M82 (Figure 3A). Salinity decreased the fruit citrate concentrations only in the wild Penn rootstocks compared to the control conditions, while it reduced the fruit succinate levels of the two grafts most frequently visited by bumblebees, the Pimpi and 77×M82 grafts, as well as K×Pimpi (Figure 3B).

3.3.3. Amino Acids

The concentrations of amino acids in the fruits were generally lower in the SG and Penn rootstocks compared to the other graft combinations, under both the control and salt stress conditions, with the exception of Tyr (Figure 3A). Notably, most amino acids showed a negative correlation with pollinator preference, being particularly significant in the case of proline in nonsalinized fruits (VN, $r = -0.75, p \leq 0.01$; TVT, $r = -0.77, p \leq 0.01$) (Table S1).

Fruits from grafted plants exposed to 75 mM NaCl generally exhibited lower amino acid concentrations relative to the control conditions, except Met, Val, and Pro, which increased under the stress treatment (Figure 3B). In the salinized grafted plants, the fruit Arg, His, Gln, Val, Met, Asn, Leu, and Pro levels were higher in plants grafted onto hybrid rootstocks (especially K×Pimpi) compared to the SG and wild ones (Figure 3A). The salinized fruits of K×Pimpi rootstocks exhibited the largest concentrations of aromatic amino acids (Trp and Phe) along with Asp levels, while registering the lowest Tyr concentrations. Additionally, Tyr was the amino acid that showed the highest positive correlation with pollinator preference under salinity (NV, $r = 0.35, p = 0.21$; TVT, $r = 0.27, p = 0.36$) (Table S1).

In summary, under saline conditions, the rootstock that experienced the longest bumblebee visitation exhibited lower sugar concentrations but higher levels of both malate and fumarate. Among the amino acids, only Tyr was positively correlated with pollinator preference under salinity.

3.4. Fruit Mineral Composition

3.4.1. Sodium

Irrespective of the treatment, the fruits of all graft combinations accumulated significantly more Na than the SG, especially the K×Pimpi rootstocks (Figure 4A). Salt stress induced a significant increase (3.3 times) in the fruit Na concentrations in all experimental rootstocks, but the two preferred rootstock genotypes, Pimpi and, particularly, 77×M82, reached the highest concentrations (Figure 4A). Under salinity, there were positive correlations between Na and pollinator preferences (VN, $r = 0.38, p = 0.18$; TVT, $r = 0.42, p = 0.14$) under salinity (Table S1).

Figure 4. Mineral nutrient concentrations ((A–H): macronutrients and (I–L): micronutrients) in the tomato fruit juice of the cv. Unidarkwin self-grafted (SG) and grafted onto different rootstock genotypes (see Table 1) and grown under control (0 mM NaCl; green) and saline (75 mM NaCl added to the nutrient solution; pink) conditions. Boxplots represent the means of the absolute values of three replicates. Significant differences among rootstock genotypes are indicated by different letters and between treatments within each genotype by asterisks (“*” = $p \leq 0.05$; “**” = $p \leq 0.01$ and “****” = $p \leq 0.001$).

3.4.2. Nitrogen, Carbon, and Phosphorus

The fruit C and P concentrations were not affected by the graft combination or the salt treatment (Figure 4C,D; Table S2). However, fruit N concentrations were significantly affected by both factors, with the highly preferred 77×M82 rootstocks registering the highest N concentrations under suboptimal saline conditions (Figure 4B). Salinity provoked an increase in N levels relative to the control conditions, but this increase was 27.2% higher in 77×M82 with respect to the remaining graft combinations (Figure 4B). Curiously, the

two highly preferred 77×M82 and Pimpi rootstocks registered the highest increase (but nonsignificant) in fruit P concentrations under salinity compared to normal conditions. Additionally, N (VN, $r = -0.58$, $p = 0.06$; TVT, $r = 0.49$, $p = 0.12$), C (NV, $r = -0.42$, $p = 0.19$; TVT, $r = -0.48$, $p = 0.14$), and, particularly, P (VN, $r = -0.75$, $p \leq 0.01$; TVT, $r = -0.74$, $p \leq 0.01$) correlated negatively with both VN and TVT in nonsalinized fruits, while positive correlations were found between these macronutrients and VN (C, $r = 0.49$, $p = 0.07$; N, $r = 0.49$, $p = 0.07$; P, $r = 0.50$, $p = 0.07$) in salinized fruits (Table S1).

3.4.3. Potassium, Magnesium, Calcium, and Sulfur

Under the control conditions, K and Mg exhibited similar accumulation patterns in fruit juice, with Penn and especially 76×Pimpi showing highest levels (Figure 4E,F). Under salinity, K and Mg significantly increased in plants grafted onto Pimpi compared to the control. Similarly, to Mg and K, the highest Ca was found in the lowly preferred 76×Pimpi grafts under the optimal conditions (Figure 4G). Finally, the S concentrations in the tomato juice was not affected by either the genotype and only the salinized fruits of the highly-visited Pimpi increased in the concentration of S compared to the control plants (Figure 4H; Table S2). Furthermore, pollinator preferences exhibited a significant negative correlation with K (VN, $r = -0.92$, $p \leq 0.01$; TVT, $r = -0.81$, $p \leq 0.01$), Mg (VN, $r = -0.83$, $p \leq 0.01$; TVT, $r = -0.77$, $p \leq 0.01$), and S (VN, $r = -0.72$, $p \leq 0.05$; TVT, $r = -0.83$, $p \leq 0.01$) in nonstressed fruits, while showing positive correlations with Ca (VN, $r = 0.45$, $p = 0.07$) and S (VN, $r = 0.35$, $p = 0.21$; TVT, $r = 0.37$, $p = 0.19$) in stressed fruits (Table S1).

3.4.4. Micronutrients

Among micronutrients, Zn displayed the highest concentration in fruits of the less-visited 76×Pimpi grafts compared to the other rootstocks under normal growing conditions but was the most negatively reduced by salinity (Figure 4J). The Fe and Mn concentrations were not affected by genotype (Figure 4I,K; Table S2), while all graft combinations exhibited higher concentrations of these two micronutrients in salinized fruits compared to the SG plants. Salinity also increased the fruit B (28.6% on average) concentrations in all grafted plants, but these increases were significant only in the SG plants (Figure 4L). Under the control conditions, the Mn levels in the fruits were negatively correlated with both VN ($r = -0.77$, $p \leq 0.01$) and TVT ($r = -0.70$, $p \leq 0.05$) in the nonstressed fruits. Conversely, the frequency of pollinator visits was highly positively correlated with the micronutrients Fe ($r = 0.94$, $p < 0.001$) and Mn ($r = 0.55$, $p \leq 0.05$) in the salinized tomatoes (Table S1).

Overall, the longest visited rootstocks (77×M82) showed the highest concentrations of Na along with the main macronutrients N, P, and K in fruits under salinity. In general, the correlations between the nutrients analyzed in the fruits and both VN and TVT were opposite between the treatments, being negative under the control and positive under the salinity conditions.

3.5. Principal Component Analysis of Fruit Composition in Relation to Pollinator Preference

Under the control conditions, the number (VN) and duration (TVT) of visits showed a covariation with the hormones ABA and GA4, as well as hexose concentrations, in fruits along PC1, which explained 30.04% of the variability. These parameters were also clustered with the amino acids Gln and Asn, while the majority of nutrients were clustered in the opposite direction (Figure 5A). Under salinity, pollinator preferences covaried with the concentrations of the amino acid Tyr and the hormones ABA, SA, and ZR, as well as the organic acids malate and fumarate in the fruits along PC1, which explained 39.74% of the variability. Unlike the control conditions, VN and TVT were clustered with most of the macro- and micronutrients. In contrast, the majority of amino acids, except Tyr, were clustered in the direction opposite to bumblebee preferences (Figure 5B).

Figure 5. Two axes of a principal component (PC1 and PC2) analysis showing the position of all variables (denoted by abbreviations) in relation to the pollinator preference parameters (VN and TVT) under the (A) optimal and (B) salinity conditions. (A) Under the optimal conditions, the yellow triangles, purple stars, red diamonds, green circles, and blue rectangles indicate the variables belonging to clusters 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively (80% confidence level). (B) Under the salinity treatment, the blue triangles, green circles, and red diamonds indicate the variables belonging to clusters 1, 2, and 3, respectively (80% confidence level). Abbreviations as in Figures 2 and 3.

4. Discussion

4.1. Heterografting on Wild-Derived Rootstocks Enhances Fruit Composition

The rootstock genotype affects various physiological and biochemical pathways in the scion, including fruit composition and quality [18]. Indeed, the concentrations of hormones,

primary metabolites, and mineral nutrients in the tomato fruit juice of the commercial variety were affected by the rootstock genotype. While there are numerous studies investigating the impact of rootstocks on hormone concentrations in leaves, information on mature fruits is scarce [38]. In this study, heterografting significantly affected the hormonal composition of tomato juice, particularly when plants were grafted onto the wild Pimpi and the hybrids K×Pimpi, 76×Pimpi, and 77×M82 under the salinity conditions (Figure 2), thus influencing fruit properties. For instance, fruits from the Pimpi grafts registered the highest concentrations of SA (Figure 2C), a hormone that promotes fruit growth and development, alleviates stress, and improves postharvest quality by delaying senescence and reducing respiration rates [39–41]. This work also identified gibberellins (GA3 and GA4) in tomato juice, with GA3 being highly concentrated (Figure 2G). Interestingly, K×Pimpi rootstocks induced the accumulation of the growth-promoting hormones tZ (under the control conditions) and GA3 (under both the control and salinity conditions) (Figure 2D,G). ABA is a phytohormone associated with the onset of ripening [42] but also responds to stress [37,43]. However, fruit ABA under salt stress only increased in the 77×M82 grafts, while it was reduced in the self-grafts (Figure 2B).

Tomato taste and flavor are influenced by sugars, organic acids, amino acids, and volatile compounds (VOCs) [44,45]. Generally, fruits from the heterografted plants showed an increase in hexoses, at the expense of sucrose, under the control conditions and an increase in fumarate and malate under salinity conditions (Figure 3A). Curiously, fruits from plants grafted onto the wild tomato Penn registered higher levels of organic acids (fumarate, malate, and citrate), mainly under the optimal growing conditions (Figure 3A), suggesting that this wild rootstock can improve fruit quality in the absence of stress. Similarly, several amino acids, such as Phe, Leu, and Val, increased in the heterografts under both the optimal and salinity growing conditions, while salinized fruits from the K×Pimpi grafts exhibited the highest amino acid concentrations but the lowest for Tyr. Phe and Leu are precursors of essential VOCs that contribute to tomato flavor [46]. Under salt stress, the heterografts (mainly hybrid rootstocks) also showed higher concentrations of Pro, which serves as an osmotic adjuster and a reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenger [47,48], and of the aromatic amino acid Trp, whose derivatives like serotonin are beneficial functional food components [49]. The observed grafting-mediated enrichment of flavor and function-related compounds benefits tomato organoleptic and nutritional value.

The fruit ionome revealed that Na concentrations were higher in all heterograft combinations under both the control and salt stress conditions, suggesting a positive influence of the wild genome of the salt-adapted species on Na transport to the scion (Figure 4). While some studies have shown reduced Na in fruit from grafted plants [50], our findings suggest that certain rootstock genotypes, especially wild-derived tomatoes, improve nutrient uptake and transport under salinity stress [51]. Importantly, a rootstock-mediated increase in fruit total N was registered under salt stress (except for the Penn grafts), suggesting improved N uptake and transport under NaCl stress. Additionally several rootstocks enhanced K under control (Penn and 76×Pimpi) and/or saline (Penn, Pimpi, and 77×M82) conditions, which is the main contributor to salty flavor and increases concentration of citrate, malate and sugars [52,53]. Other rootstocks also facilitated the accumulation of Ca and Zn in the fruit, which are important for preventing disorders like “blossom-end rot” and in the overall fruit quality.

In conclusion, heterografting on particularly wild-derived rootstocks can significantly enhance the nutritional and commercial qualities of tomato fruits by influencing hormonal and metabolite profiles.

4.2. Impact of Salinity on Fruit Composition

Salinity is a critical environmental stress that profoundly affects the biochemical composition of tomato fruits, impacting both metabolite profiles and hormonal balances [54,55]. This study reveals significant changes in fruit hormonal profiles under saline conditions, with notable decreases in ACC, ZR, SA, and ABA (Figure 2; Table S2). Ethylene, a key regulator

of climacteric ripening [56], shows increased levels of its precursor, ACC, in response to stress. However, our study observed reduced ACC levels in salinized mature tomato fruits (Figure 2A), in contrast with previous findings that report increases in ACC and ethylene synthesis and signaling, which are related to a shortened shelf-life [57,58]. Although the timing of the ripening was not studied, the results suggest that reduced ACC evolution could improve shelf-life-related physicochemical properties. CKs, which regulate tomato fruit growth and development [59], were also affected by the salinity. The reductions in ZR in the salinized fruits agree with the findings in leaves [60,61], linked to an accelerated senescence, reducing cell division and delaying aging. The observed decrease in ZR levels in our study could be attributed to several mechanisms (affected by salinity), including oxidative stress, altered hormone translocation, increased degradation of cytokinins, and conversion of ZR to t-Z [62].

Contrary to the usual trends in SA accumulation in response to stress, a decrease in SA levels has also been reported in the leaves of *Iris hexagona* L. [63] and in tomato culture cells [64] exposed to salt stress. This reduction might indicate an adaptive response, with SA potentially involved in stress adaptation mechanisms. Similarly, ABA, which generally increase in salinized fruits [55,65], was found to decrease in tomato fruits under high salinity conditions (Figure 2B). The reductions in ABA in the tomato fruits under the salinity conditions in our study may represent an adaptive response to prolong fruit development and ensure fruit quality under suboptimal conditions [66].

Sugars and organic acids are key components of soluble solids in tomato fruit and crucial for fruit quality [67]. Malate and fumarate (Figure 3B), crucial intermediates in the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and overall fruit metabolism [68], decreased under salinity conditions. This reduction can be attributed to a shift in the TCA pathways, redirecting precursors toward the synthesis of defense compounds and osmo protectants [68]. Indeed, oxalic acid serves as a precursor to Asp, which subsequently acts as a precursor to Met, and our results showed an increase in Met levels under saline conditions (Figure 3B). Although amino acid levels were generally lower compared to the control conditions, proline notably accumulated in the fruits under salinity, aligning with its known role in plant responses to abiotic stress.

Mineral composition was also affected by salinity. The results show that salinity increases Na levels (Figure 4A) in tomato fruits [54,69,70] and also raised N levels (Figure 4B), likely due to altered nitrogen metabolism and/or to a reduction in the fruit growth [71]. Higher Na levels can compete with the absorption of other nutrients such as K and Ca, increasing nitrogen uptake to maintain cellular function and photosynthesis [72]. Indeed, our study observed a decrease in Ca and K concentrations in the fruits of several tomato genotypes. Similarly, NaCl significantly increased Mg and B levels (Figure 4F,L) in fruits. Mg plays a critical role in chlorophyll synthesis and photosynthesis, [73] while B is essential for cell wall stability, which directly influences fruit development and structural integrity [73]. The observed increases in Mg and B under saline conditions suggest that the plant may be mobilizing these nutrients to sustain fruit development and maintain fruit quality despite the stress.

Overall, the results highlight the complex alterations under salinity of the different components of the fruits' compositions because of adaptive mechanisms and altered metabolic and growth processes that affect fruit size and quality.

4.3. Relationships between Pollinator Preferences and Fruit Compositions

Pollinators increase crop yields [26,31,74,75] and enhance fruit quality traits such as color, shape, and size [32,76,77]. While the impact of pollination on nutritional quality of fruit has been studied [30,77–81], there is limited research focusing on primary and secondary metabolites in fruit related to pollinator foraging choices and, particularly, in grafted tomatoes [33]. In the present study, pollinator activity was correlated with changes in the concentrations of several metabolites, as well as the nutrients, in the tomato fruit juice mediated by the rootstock and or the saline treatment.

Pollinator foraging behavior was associated with the concentrations of several hormones in fruits of grafted plants subjected to salinity (Figure 5B; Table S1). For instance, a positive correlation was found between the cytokinin ZR and the number and duration of visit to salinized fruits (Table S2). CKs play an important role in regulating flower development [82–84] and could improve the attractiveness to a pollinator by enhancing floral traits. On the other hand, ABA levels increased in the salinized fruits of the preferred grafts like Pimpi and 77×M82 in response to saline conditions (Figure 1B), correlating positively with the total visiting time (Figure 5B; Table S1). In addition to ABA role in stress responses associated with salinity or drought [85], ABA also regulates multiple functions related to reproductive development (flower transition, embryo morphogenesis, and seed maturation) and can accelerate bud development through exogenous foliar application [86]. Consistent with our results, we might suggest that ABA in the fruit is an indicator of longer visit durations. Additionally, the SA concentrations in the fruit, along with the levels of ABA and ZR, were the only hormones than covaried with pollinator preferences. SA's involvement in the production of primary metabolites and VOCs [87] may indicate the presence of VOCs in sink organs, which attracts pollinators [34].

Pollinator preferences (VN and TVT) were clustered with hexose concentration under the control conditions (Figure 5A) when assimilate availability was not disturbed by the stress. Although it is difficult to accept that similar metabolic alterations occur in flowers and fruits, the prolonged visitation by bumblebees to the rootstock 77×M82 under saline conditions suggests that despite the lower sugar concentrations in the fruit, other factors such as the presence of organic acids (malate and fumarate) might be playing a role in attracting and retaining pollinators. Malate and fumarate are known to contribute to the overall taste and nutritional profile of pollen, nectar, and fruit, potentially influencing pollinator preferences [88]. Additionally Tyr, an amino acid precursor of VOCs [89,90] and neurohormonal compounds in bees as dopamine and tyramine [91], were the only amino acid positively correlated with pollinator preferences under salinity, potentially enhancing the appeal of these plants to pollinators. Tyr is also present in honeybees' royal jelly, and the intake affects bees' behavior [91]. Sodium, is an essential nutrient for pollinators and other animals like herbivores. The observed positive correlation between fruit Na content under salinity and pollinator preference aligns with studies on nectar from wild species pollinated by different pollinators, including *Bombus* species [19,92]. Furthermore, macronutrients and micronutrients were clustered together with pollinator preference parameters (VN and TVT) (Figure 5B). Although there is limited research on how the minerals in the fruit vary with pollination, the role of mineral distribution in fruits on foraging decisions have been shown for apple [93]. Specifically, K and micronutrients such as Mg and Zn align with our findings under salinity conditions, where K and Mg significantly increased in plants grafted onto the preferred rootstock Pimpi. Interestingly, contents of Mg, Zn, and Ca in apples are influenced by animal pollination [76], further supporting the significance of pollination in the distribution of minerals in fruits.

The results indicate that pollinator preferences are closely linked to specific fruit metabolites and nutrients influenced by rootstock genotype and salinity. Factors like SA, ABA, and certain amino acids may attract and retain pollinators, emphasizing the need to consider these in managing crop quality and pollinator interactions to enhance agricultural outcomes.

5. Conclusions

Both grafting and soil salinity significantly influenced fruit juice composition, demonstrating the importance for growers to choose a suitable rootstock (wild or hybrid) to keep adequate levels of metabolites of interest, like sugars, organic acids, and minerals, in fruits. Although fruit juice composition could only be indirectly related to the foraging behavior of pollinators, as the nutritional reward and other floral signals that bumblebees receive were not studied here, our findings indicate plant hormones, such as ABA, ZR, and SA, as well as macro- and micronutrients and primary metabolites (fumarate, malate, and Tyr) in

fruit juice as factors associated with pollinators' preferences. Unlike open-field studies in which pollinator activity is difficult to monitor precisely, our study utilized an advanced technology to accurately track the plants visited and the durations of the visits by each monitored bumblebee. Additionally, we employed targeted metabolomics to precisely quantify the concentrations of primary metabolites in tomato juice.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/horticulturae10090992/s1>, Table S1: Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for visit number (NV) and total visit time (TVT) with metabolites and nutrients under the optimal conditions and salt stress (75 mM NaCl) conditions. *p*-Values < 0.05 are indicated in bold. Abbreviations as in Figures 2 and 3; Table S2: *p*-Values from the multivariate ANOVA for plant hormone, organic acid, amino acid, sugar, and nutrient concentrations in tomato fruits. Significant differences (*p* < 0.05) are indicated in bold.

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References

- Li, Y.; Wang, H.; Zhang, Y.; Martin, C. Can the world's favorite fruit, tomato, provide an effective biosynthetic chassis for high-value metabolites? *Plant Cell Rep.* **2018**, *37*, 1443–1450. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Quinet, M.; Angosto, T.; Yuste-Lisbona, F.J.; Blanchard-Gros, R.; Bigot, S.; Martinez, J.-P.; Lutts, S. Tomato Fruit Development and Metabolism. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 1554. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Behera, T.K.; Krishna, R.; Ansari, W.A.; Aamir, M.; Kumar, P.; Kashyap, S.P.; Pandey, S.; Kole, C. Approaches Involved in the Vegetable Crops Salt Stress Tolerance Improvement: Present Status and Way Ahead. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2022**, *12*, 787292. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Ehtaiwesh, A.F. The effect of salinity on nutrient availability and uptake in crop plants. *J. Appl. Sci.* **2022**, *55*–73. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Christou, A.; Manganaris, G.A.; Papadopoulos, I.; Fotopoulos, V. Hydrogen sulfide induces systemic tolerance to salinity and non-ionic osmotic stress in strawberry plants through modification of reactive species biosynthesis and transcriptional regulation of multiple defence pathways. *J. Exp. Bot.* **2013**, *64*, 1953–1966. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Ruiz, M.S.; Yasuor, H.; Ben-Gal, A.; Yermiyahu, U.; Saranga, Y.; Elbaum, R. Salinity induced fruit hypodermis thickening alters the texture of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* Mill) fruits. *Sci. Hort.* **2015**, *192*, 244–249. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Yaghubi, K.; Ghaderi, N.; Vafae, Y.; Javadi, T. Potassium silicate alleviates deleterious effects of salinity on two strawberry cultivars grown under soilless pot culture. *Sci. Hort.* **2016**, *213*, 87–95. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Abdel-Farid, I.B.; Marghany, M.R.; Rowezek, M.M.; Sheded, M.G. Effect of Salinity Stress on Growth and Metabolomic Profiling of *Cucumis sativus* and *Solanum lycopersicum*. *Plants* **2020**, *9*, 1626. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Magán, J.J.; Gallardo, M.; Thompson, R.B.; Lorenzo, P. Effects of salinity on fruit yield and quality of tomato grown in soil-less culture in greenhouses in Mediterranean climatic conditions. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2008**, *95*, 1041–1055. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Zhang, P.; Senge, M.; Yoshiyama, K.; Ito, K.; Dai, Y.; Zhang, F. Effects of Low Salinity Stress on Growth, Yield and Water Use Efficiency of Tomato under Soilless Cultivation. *Proc. Agric. Rural. Eng. Soc.* **2017**, *85*, I_15–I_21. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Al-Gaadi, K.A.; Tola, E.; Madugundu, R.; Zeyada, A.M.; Alameen, A.A.; Edris, M.K.; Edrees, H.F.; Mahjoop, O. Response of leaf photosynthesis, chlorophyll content and yield of hydroponic tomatoes to different water salinity levels. *PLoS ONE* **2024**, *19*, e0293098. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

12. Aydin, A. Effects of grafting with wild tomato (*Solanum pimpinellifolium* and *Solanum habrochaites*) rootstocks on growth and leaf mineral accumulation in salt stress. *Hortic. Environ. Biotechnol.* **2024**, *10*, 1–17. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Coban, A.; Akhoundnejad, Y.; Dere, S.; Yildiz Dasgan, H. Impact of Salt-tolerant Rootstock on the Enhancement of Sensitive Tomato Plant Responses to Salinity. *HortScience* **2020**, *55*, 35–39. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Ingram, T.W.; Sharpe, S.; Trandel, M.; Perkins-Veazie, P.; Louws, F.J.; Meadows, I. Vigorous rootstocks improve yields and increase fruit sizes in grafted fresh market tomatoes. *Front. Hortic.* **2022**, *1*, 1091342. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Savvas, D.; Öztekin, G.B.; Tepecik, M.; Ropokis, A.; Tüzel, Y.; Ntatsi, G.; Schwarz, D. Impact of grafting and rootstock on nutrient-to-water uptake ratios during the first month after planting of hydroponically grown tomato. *J. Hortic. Sci. Biotechnol.* **2017**, *92*, 294–302. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Gisbert-Mullor, R.; Ceccanti, C.; Gara Padilla, Y.; López-Galarza, S.; Calatayud, Á.; Conte, G.; Guidi, L. Effect of Grafting on the Production, Physico-Chemical Characteristics and Nutritional Quality of Fruit from Pepper Landraces. *Antioxidants* **2020**, *9*, 501. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Kyriacou, M.C.; Roupael, Y.; Colla, G.; Zrenner, R.; Schwarz, D. Vegetable Grafting: The Implications of a Growing Agronomic Imperative for Vegetable Fruit Quality and Nutritive Value. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2017**, *8*, 741. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Morales Alfaro, J.; Bermejo, A.; Navarro, P.; Quiñones, A.; Salvador, A. Effect of Rootstock on Citrus Fruit Quality: A Review. *Food Rev. Int.* **2023**, *39*, 2835–2853. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Finkelstein, C.J.; CaraDonna, P.J.; Gruver, A.; Welti, E.A.R.; Kaspari, M.; Sanders, N.J. Sodium-enriched floral nectar increases pollinator visitation rate and diversity. *Biol. Lett.* **2022**, *18*, 20220016. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Marroquin, A.; Holmes, K.; Salazar, D. Soil salinization and chemically mediated plant–insect interactions in a changing climate. *Curr. Opin. Insect Sci.* **2023**, *60*, 101130. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Colin, L.; Ruhnnow, F.; Zhu, J.-K.; Zhao, C.; Zhao, Y.; Persson, S. The cell biology of primary cell walls during salt stress. *Plant Cell* **2023**, *35*, 201–217. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
22. Vaudo, A.D.; Patch, H.M.; Mortensen, D.A.; Tooker, J.F.; Grozinger, C.M. Macronutrient ratios in pollen shape bumble bee (*Bombus impatiens*) foraging strategies and floral preferences. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2016**, *113*, E4035–E4042. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
23. Bishop, J.; Garratt, M.P.D.; Nakagawa, S. Animal pollination increases stability of crop yield across spatial scales. *Ecol. Lett.* **2022**, *25*, 2034–2047. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
24. Potts, S.G.; Biesmeijer, J.C.; Kremen, C.; Neumann, P.; Schweiger, O.; Kunin, W.E. Global pollinator declines: Trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **2010**, *25*, 345–353. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Adamidis, G.C.; Cartar, R.V.; Melathopoulos, A.P.; Pernal, S.F.; Hoover, S.E. Pollinators enhance crop yield and shorten the growing season by modulating plant functional characteristics: A comparison of 23 canola varieties. *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9*, 14208. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Garibaldi, L.A.; Steffan-Dewenter, I.; Winfree, R.; Aizen, M.A.; Bommarco, R.; Cunningham, S.A.; Kremen, C.; Carvalheiro, L.G.; Harder, L.D.; Afik, O.; et al. Wild Pollinators Enhance Fruit Set of Crops Regardless of Honey Bee Abundance. *Science* **2013**, *339*, 1608–1611. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Cooley, H.; Vallejo-Marín, M. Buzz-Pollinated Crops: A Global Review and Meta-analysis of the Effects of Supplemental Bee Pollination in Tomato. *J. Econ. Entomol.* **2021**, *114*, 505–519. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Toni, H.C.; Djossa, B.A.; Ayenan, M.A.T.; Teka, O. Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) pollinators and their effect on fruit set and quality. *J. Hortic. Sci. Biotechnol.* **2021**, *96*, 1–13. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Yoon, H.J.; Park, I.G. Current Status and Agricultural Utilization of Insect Pollinators in Korea. 2019. Available online: https://www.naro.affrc.go.jp/archive/niaes/sinfo/sympo/h22/1109/paper_07.pdf (accessed on 30 July 2024).
30. Abrol, D.P.; Gorka, A.K.; Ansari, M.J.; Al-Ghamdi, A.; Al-Kahtani, S. Impact of insect pollinators on yield and fruit quality of strawberry. *Saudi J. Biol. Sci.* **2019**, *26*, 524–530. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Cortés-Rivas, B.; Monzón, V.H.; Rego, J.O.; Mesquita-Neto, J.N. Pollination by native bees achieves high fruit quantity and quality of highbush blueberry: A sustainable alternative to managed pollinators. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2023**, *7*, 1142623. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Gudowska, A.; Cwajna, A.; Marjańska, E.; Moroń, D. Pollinators enhance the production of a superior strawberry—A global review and meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* **2024**, *362*, 108815. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Zhang, H.; Han, C.; Breeze, T.D.; Li, M.; Mashilingi, S.K.; Hua, J.; Zhang, W.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, S.; An, J. Bumblebee Pollination Enhances Yield and Flavor of Tomato in Gobi Desert Greenhouses. *Agriculture* **2022**, *12*, 795. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Borghi, M.; Perez de Souza, L.; Yoshida, T.; Fernie, A.R. Flowers and climate change: A metabolic perspective. *New Phytol.* **2019**, *224*, 1425–1441. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
35. Hoagland, D.R.; Arnon, D.I. *The Water-Culture Method for Growing Plants without Soil*; Circular-347; California Agricultural Experiment Station: Davis, CA, USA, 1950.
36. Pérez-Alfocea, F.; Borghi, M.; Guerrero, J.J.; Jiménez, A.R.; Jiménez-Gómez, J.M.; Fernie, A.R.; Bartomeus, I. Pollinator-assisted plant phenotyping, selection, and breeding for crop resilience to abiotic stresses. *Plant J.* **2024**, *119*, tpe16748. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
37. Albacete, A.; Ghanem, M.E.; Martínez-Andujar, C.; Acosta, M.; Sanchez-Bravo, J.; Martínez, V.; Lutts, S.; Dodd, I.C.; Perez-Alfocea, F. Hormonal changes in relation to biomass partitioning and shoot growth impairment in salinized tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) plants. *J. Exp. Bot.* **2008**, *59*, 4119–4131. [[CrossRef](#)]

38. Martínez-Andújar, C.; Martínez-Pérez, A.; Albacete, A.; Martínez-Melgarejo, P.A.; Dodd, I.C.; Thompson, A.J.; Mohareb, F.; Estelles-Lopez, L.; Kevei, Z.; Ferrández-Ayela, A.; et al. Overproduction of ABA in rootstocks alleviates salinity stress in tomato shoots. *Plant Cell Environ.* **2021**, *44*, 2966–2986. [CrossRef]
39. Frick, E.M.; Sapkota, M.; Pereira, L.; Wang, Y.; Hermanns, A.; Giovannoni, J.J.; Van Der Knaap, E.; Tieman, D.M.; Klee, H.J. A family of methyl esterases converts methyl salicylate to salicylic acid in ripening tomato fruit. *Plant Physiol.* **2023**, *191*, 110–124. [CrossRef]
40. Hayat, S.; Ahmad, A.; Alyemeni, M.N. Salicylic Acid: Plant Growth and Development. *Springer Science & Business Media*. 2013. Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/232250198_Salicylic_Acid_Plant_Growth_and_Development (accessed on 30 July 2024).
41. Souri, M.K.; Tohidloo, G. Effectiveness of different methods of salicylic acid application on growth characteristics of tomato seedlings under salinity. *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.* **2019**, *6*, 26. [CrossRef]
42. Upadhyay, R.K.; Motyka, V.; Pokorná, E.; Filepová, R.; Dobrev, P.I.; Handa, A.K.; Mattoo, A.K. A comprehensive endogenous phytohormone metabolite landscape identifies new metabolites associated with tomato fruit. *Plant Growth Regul.* **2024**. [CrossRef]
43. Lovelli, S.; Scopa, A.; Perniola, M.; Di Tommaso, T.; Sofo, A. Abscisic acid root and leaf concentration in relation to biomass partitioning in salinized tomato plants. *J. Plant Physiol.* **2012**, *169*, 226–233. [CrossRef]
44. Bastías, A.; López-Climent, M.; Valcárcel, M.; Rosello, S.; Gómez-Cadenas, A.; Casaretto, J.A. Modulation of organic acids and sugar content in tomato fruits by an abscisic acid-regulated transcription factor. *Physiol. Plant.* **2011**, *141*, 215–226. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
45. Sorrequieta, A.; Ferraro, G.; Boggio, S.B.; Valle, E.M. Free amino acid production during tomato fruit ripening: A focus on l-glutamate. *Amino Acids* **2010**, *38*, 1523–1532. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
46. Wang, S.; Qiang, Q.; Xiang, L.; Fernie, A.R.; Yang, J. Targeted approaches to improve tomato fruit taste. *Hortic. Res.* **2023**, *10*, uhac229. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
47. Khan, N.; Ali, S.; Zandi, P.; Mehmood, A.; Ullah, S.; Ikram, M.; Ismail, I.; Shahid, M.A.; Babar, M.A. Role of sugars, amino acids and organic acids in improving plant abiotic stress tolerance. *Pak. J. Bot.* **2020**, *52*, 355–363. [CrossRef]
48. Pérez-Alfocea, F.; Larher, F. Sucrose and proline accumulation and sugar efflux in tomato leaf discs affected by NaCl and polyethylene glycol 6000 iso-osmotic stresses. *Plant Sci.* **1995**, *107*, 9–15. [CrossRef]
49. Hano, S.; Shibuya, T.; Imoto, N.; Ito, A.; Imanishi, S.; Aso, H.; Kanayama, Y. Serotonin content in fresh and processed tomatoes and its accumulation during fruit development. *Sci. Hortic.* **2017**, *214*, 107–113. [CrossRef]
50. Di Gioia, F.; Signore, A.; Serio, F.; Santamaria, P. Grafting Improves Tomato Salinity Tolerance through Sodium Partitioning within the Shoot. *HortScience* **2013**, *48*, 855–862. [CrossRef]
51. Alfocea, F.P.; Balibrea, M.E.; Alarcón, J.J.; Bolarín, M.C. Composition of Xylem and Phloem Exudates in Relation to the Salt-tolerance of Domestic and Wild Tomato Species. *J. Plant Physiol.* **2000**, *156*, 367–374. [CrossRef]
52. Sainju, U.M.; Dris, R.; Singh, B. Mineral Nutrition of Tomato. *J. Food Agric. Environ.* **2003**, *1*, 176–183.
53. Salles, C.; Nicklaus, S.; Septier, C. Determination and gustatory properties of taste-active compounds in tomato juice. *Food Chem.* **2003**, *81*, 395–402. [CrossRef]
54. Agius, C.; Von Tucher, S.; Rozhon, W. The Effect of Salinity on Fruit Quality and Yield of Cherry Tomatoes. *Horticulturae* **2022**, *8*, 59. [CrossRef]
55. Babu, M.A.; Singh, D.; Gothandam, K.M. The Effect of Salinity on Growth, Hormones and Mineral Elements in Leaf and Fruit of Tomato Cultivar PKM1. *J. Anim. Plant Sci.* **2012**, *22*, 159–164. Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231167031_The_effect_of_salinity_on_growth_hormones_and_mineral_elements_in_leaf_and_fruit_of_tomato_cultivar_PKM1 (accessed on 30 July 2024).
56. Paul, M.; Van Hekken, D.L. Short communication: Assessing antihypertensive activity in native and model Queso Fresco cheeses. *J. Dairy Sci.* **2011**, *94*, 2280–2284. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
57. Botella, M.Á.; Del Amor, F.; Amorós, A.; Serrano, M.; Martínez, V.; Cerdá, A. Polyamine, ethylene and other physico-chemical parameters in tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) fruits as affected by salinity. *Physiol. Plant.* **2000**, *109*, 428–434. [CrossRef]
58. Takács, Z.; Czékus, Z.; Tari, I.; Poór, P. The role of ethylene signalling in the regulation of salt stress response in mature tomato fruits: Metabolism of antioxidants and polyamines. *J. Plant Physiol.* **2022**, *277*, 153793. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
59. Gan, L.; Song, M.; Wang, X.; Yang, N.; Li, H.; Liu, X.; Li, Y. Cytokinins are involved in regulation of tomato pericarp thickness and fruit size. *Hortic. Res.* **2022**, *9*, uhab041. [CrossRef]
60. Albacete, A.; Martínez-Andújar, C.; Ghanem, M.E.; Acosta, M.; Sánchez-Bravo, J.; Asins, M.J.; Cuartero, J.; Lutts, S.; Dodd, I.C.; Pérez-Alfocea, F. Rootstock-mediated changes in xylem ionic and hormonal status are correlated with delayed leaf senescence, and increased leaf area and crop productivity in salinized tomato. *Plant Cell Environ.* **2009**, *32*, 928–938. [CrossRef]
61. Ghanem, M.E.; Hichri, I.; Smigocki, A.C.; Albacete, A.; Fauconnier, M.-L.; Diatloff, E.; Martínez-Andujar, C.; Lutts, S.; Dodd, I.C.; Pérez-Alfocea, F. Root-targeted biotechnology to mediate hormonal signalling and improve crop stress tolerance. *Plant Cell Rep.* **2011**, *30*, 807–823. [CrossRef]
62. Yu, Y.; Li, Y.; Yan, Z.; Duan, X. The Role of Cytokinins in Plant Under Salt Stress. *J. Plant Growth Regul.* **2022**, *41*, 2279–2291. [CrossRef]
63. Wang, Y.; Mopper, S.; Hasenstein, K.H. Effects of salinity on endogenous ABA, IAA, JA, and SA in *Iris hexagona*. *J. Chem. Ecol.* **2001**, *27*, 327–342. [CrossRef]

64. Molina, A.; Bueno, P.; Marín, M.C.; Rodríguez-Rosales, M.P.; Belver, A.; Venema, K.; Donaire, J.P. Involvement of endogenous salicylic acid content, lipoxygenase and antioxidant enzyme activities in the response of tomato cell suspension cultures to NaCl. *New Phytol.* **2002**, *156*, 409–415. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
65. Perin, E.C.; Da Silva Messias, R.; Borowski, J.M.; Crizel, R.L.; Schott, I.B.; Carvalho, I.R.; Rombaldi, C.V.; Galli, V. ABA-dependent salt and drought stress improve strawberry fruit quality. *Food Chem.* **2019**, *271*, 516–526. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
66. Kou, X.; Yang, S.; Chai, L.; Wu, C.; Zhou, J.; Liu, Y.; Xue, Z. Abscisic acid and fruit ripening: Multifaceted analysis of the effect of abscisic acid on fleshy fruit ripening. *Sci. Hort.* **2021**, *281*, 109999. [[CrossRef](#)]
67. Agius, C.; Von Tucher, S.; Poppenberger, B.; Rozhon, W. Quantification of sugars and organic acids in tomato fruits. *MethodsX* **2018**, *5*, 537–550. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Nunes-Nesi, A.; Fernie, A.R.; Stitt, M. Metabolic and Signaling Aspects Underpinning the Regulation of Plant Carbon Nitrogen Interactions. *Mol. Plant* **2010**, *3*, 973–996. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Giuffrida, F.; Martorana, M.; Leonardi, C. How Sodium Chloride Concentration in the Nutrient Solution Influences the Mineral Composition of Tomato Leaves and Fruits. *HortScience* **2009**, *44*, 707–711. [[CrossRef](#)]
70. Maggio, A.; Raimondi, G.; Martino, A.; De Pascale, S. Salt stress response in tomato beyond the salinity tolerance threshold. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* **2007**, *59*, 276–282. [[CrossRef](#)]
71. Wang, H.; Zhang, M.; Guo, R.; Shi, D.; Liu, B.; Lin, X.; Yang, C. Effects of salt stress on ion balance and nitrogen metabolism of old and young leaves in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *BMC Plant Biol.* **2012**, *12*, 194. [[CrossRef](#)]
72. *Marschner's Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2012. [[CrossRef](#)]
73. Day, S.; Aasim, M. Role of Boron in Growth and Development of Plant: Deficiency and Toxicity Perspective. In *Plant Micronutrients*; Aftab, T., Hakeem, K.R., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, Switzerland, 2020; pp. 435–453. [[CrossRef](#)]
74. Garibaldi, L.A.; Carvalheiro, L.G.; Leonhardt, S.D.; Aizen, M.A.; Blaauw, B.R.; Isaacs, R.; Kuhlmann, M.; Kleijn, D.; Klein, A.M.; Kremen, C.; et al. From research to action: Enhancing crop yield through wild pollinators. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* **2014**, *12*, 439–447. [[CrossRef](#)]
75. Klatt, B.K.; Holzschuh, A.; Westphal, C.; Clough, Y.; Smit, I.; Pawelzik, E.; Tschardt, T. Bee pollination improves crop quality, shelf life and commercial value. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **2014**, *281*, 20132440. [[CrossRef](#)]
76. Garratt, M.P.D.; Breeze, T.D.; Jenner, N.; Polce, C.; Biesmeijer, J.C.; Potts, S.G. Avoiding a bad apple: Insect pollination enhances fruit quality and economic value. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* **2014**, *184*, 34–40. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
77. Gazzea, E.; Batáry, P.; Marini, L. Global meta-analysis shows reduced quality of food crops under inadequate animal pollination. *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 4463. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
78. Botella, M.Á.; Hernández, V.; Mestre, T.; Hellín, P.; García-Legaz, M.F.; Rivero, R.M.; Martínez, V.; Fenoll, J.; Flores, P. Bioactive Compounds of Tomato Fruit in Response to Salinity, Heat and Their Combination. *Agriculture* **2021**, *11*, 534. [[CrossRef](#)]
79. Brittain, C.; Kremen, C.; Garber, A.; Klein, A.-M. Pollination and Plant Resources Change the Nutritional Quality of Almonds for Human Health. *PLoS ONE* **2014**, *9*, e90082. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
80. Monasterolo, M.; Chacoff, N.P.; Segura, Á.D.; Benavidez, A.; Schliserman, P. Native pollinators increase fruit set while honeybees decrease the quality of mandarins in family farms. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* **2022**, *64*, 79–88. [[CrossRef](#)]
81. Sagwe, R.N.; Peters, M.K.; Dubois, T.; Steffan-Dewenter, I.; Lattorff, H.M.G. Insect pollination and pollinator supplementation enhances fruit weight, quality, and marketability of avocado (*Persea americana*). *Arthropod-Plant Interact.* **2023**, *17*, 753–763. [[CrossRef](#)]
82. Denay, G.; Chahtane, H.; Tichtinsky, G.; Parcy, F. A flower is born: An update on Arabidopsis floral meristem formation. *Curr. Opin. Plant Biol.* **2017**, *35*, 15–22. [[CrossRef](#)]
83. Kieber, J.J.; Schaller, G.E. Cytokinin signaling in plant development. *Development* **2018**, *145*, dev149344. [[CrossRef](#)]
84. Wybouw, B.; De Rybel, B. Cytokinin—A Developing Story. *Trends Plant Sci.* **2019**, *24*, 177–185. [[CrossRef](#)]
85. Seo, M.; Marion-Poll, A. Abscisic acid metabolism and transport. In *Advances in Botanical Research*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2019; Volume 92, pp. 1–49. [[CrossRef](#)]
86. Sood, A.; Duchin, S.; Adamov, Z.; Carmeli-Weissberg, M.; Shaya, F.; Spitzer-Rimon, B. Abscisic acid mediates the reduction of petunia flower size at elevated temperatures due to reduced cell division. *Planta* **2022**, *255*, 18. [[CrossRef](#)]
87. Batista, V.C.V.; Pereira, I.M.C.; Paula-Marinho, S.D.O.; Canuto, K.M.; Pereira, R.D.C.A.; Rodrigues, T.H.S.; Daloso, D.D.M.; Gomes-Filho, E.; Carvalho, H.H.D. Salicylic acid modulates primary and volatile metabolites to alleviate salt stress-induced photosynthesis impairment on medicinal plant *Egletes viscosa*. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* **2019**, *167*, 103870. [[CrossRef](#)]
88. Park, Y.; Kim, J.H.; Kim, S.H. Free Sugar and Organic Acid Contents of Pollens from *Quercus* spp. in Korea. *J. Apic.* **2017**, *32*, 375–379. [[CrossRef](#)]
89. Borghi, M.; Fernie, A.R.; Schiestl, F.P.; Bouwmeester, H.J. The Sexual Advantage of Looking, Smelling, and Tasting Good: The Metabolic Network that Produces Signals for Pollinators. *Trends Plant Sci.* **2017**, *22*, 338–350. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
90. Borghi, M.; Fernie, A.R. Floral Metabolism of Sugars and Amino Acids: Implications for Pollinators' Preferences and Seed and Fruit Set. *Plant Physiol.* **2017**, *175*, 1510–1524. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
91. Matsuyama, S.; Nagao, T.; Sasaki, K. Consumption of tyrosine in royal jelly increases brain levels of dopamine and tyramine and promotes transition from normal to reproductive workers in queenless honey bee colonies. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* **2015**, *211*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

92. VanValkenburg, E.; Gonçalves Souza, T.; Sanders, N.J.; CaraDonna, P. Sodium-enriched nectar shapes plant–pollinator interactions in a subalpine meadow. *Ecol. Evol.* **2024**, *14*, e70026. [[CrossRef](#)]
93. Samnegård, U.; Hambäck, P.A.; Smith, H.G. Pollination treatment affects fruit set and modifies marketable and storable fruit quality of commercial apples. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **2019**, *6*, 190326. [[CrossRef](#)]

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